

RDA Recommendations on Remotely Piloted Aerial System data management

Log sheet and RPAS acquisition checklist

On the field, it is important to record key metadata to make sure you can process the data you have collected using your Remotely Piloted Aerial System (RPAS) and they can be reused in the future. This document comprises a checklist and logsheets you can use to best plan your survey.

How to use this document:

- Download the document
- Modify it to take into account your specific requirements
- Bring the templates with you on the field
- Use the template on the field to document the survey

Data collection checklist

Here is a list of metadata information and activity you might want to record as part of your survey:

Summary data collection document

- Project
- Survey name
- Start date/time of first flight of the survey
- End date/time of last flight of the survey
- Geographic extent of the survey
- Total numbers of flights
- Platform make and model
- Mission planning software
- List of sensors make and model and possible configurations. For each sensor, metadata might include make, model, sampling rate, resolution, measurement capability and accuracy, their location on the platform such as mount and orientation, firmware and version
- Calibration information
- General comments

Log information for each flight

- Flight ID
- Date
- Start time flight
- End time flight
- Latitude start
- Latitude end
- Longitude start
- Longitude end
- Operator name
- Weather information (visibility/cloud cover)
- Platform
- List of sensors
- Logs of events including time, comments, cause, effects of events
- Specific configuration notes (are all the sensors on for the flight?, location of the sensors on the platform)
- Calibration done/calibration flight
- Make sure it is recording data and GNSS information

UAV summary data collection

Project	
Survey name	
Date and time of first flight	
Date and time of last flight	
Total number of flights	

Geographic extent

Latitude min	
Latitude max	
Longitude min	
Longitude max	

Insert map here

Summary of the survey

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Description of the platform:

Name:
Make and model:.....
Payload:.....
Mission planning software:.....

Description of sensors:

Sensor 1

- Name:.....
- Make and model:.....
- Sampling rate:.....
- Resolution/accuracy:.....
- Location on drone:.....
- Mount and orientation:..... (here several configurations can be mentioned)
- Firmware and version:.....
- Calibration:.....

Sensor 2

- Name:.....
- Make and model:.....
- Sampling rate:.....
- Resolution/accuracy:.....
- Location on drone:.....
- Mount and orientation:..... (here several configurations can be mentioned)
- Firmware and version:.....
- Calibration:.....

Sensor 3

- Name:.....
- Make and model:.....
- Sampling rate:.....
- Resolution/accuracy:.....
- Location on drone:.....
- Mount and orientation:..... (here several configurations can be mentioned)
- Firmware and version:.....
- Calibration:.....

Calibration information:

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

